

Rendering News Credible with Efficient Gatekeeping

Jyoti Pareek

Research Scholar, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication

Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Jyotipareek29@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6093-1718>

Amit Sharma, (PhD)

Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication

Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

jmcamit@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9589-2245>

Abstract

Mainstream media is credible medium due to its effective gatekeeping process. This study applies to examine who makes news credible during gatekeeping practice in mainstream media. A survey is conducted to find out in-depth information about the gatekeeper and gatekeeping process. As per the requirement of this descriptive research, the closed-ended questionnaire is used. Results indicate that editorial staff is the most effective gatekeeper in mainstream media. The trending topics of social media become lead news in mainstream media.

Keywords: Television news, Imbalance, Mainstream media, Social media, and Digital media.

1.0 Introduction

The concept of gatekeeping was given by Kurt Lewin in the year of 1943. But it was identified in the year 1922 literature (Cherry, 2020; Steele, 2018). The initial idea of gatekeeping in reporting was founded in a specific news industry sub-profession, and a specific technological substrate (Bro & Wallberg, 2015). Gatekeepers are mainstream press experts, particularly reporters and editorial staff, who decide what topics to cover and what details to include in the articles. These gatekeepers impact the information about politics and other pressing issues that

consumers evaluate. And by extending, they impact the final results of political campaigns and elections (Lewis, 2020).

A combination of organizational considerations, new standards, and readers' interests drive the systematic bias in the stories that journalists and editors choose to publish. We know that the resulting news content tends to focus on stories that are, for example, more sensational, uncommon, and contentious, or located nearby (Soroka, 2012). Mass media is one of the best ways to disseminate information among readers, viewers, and audiences. Media can be divided into two mains i.e., mainstream media and social media. Mainstream media is more popular and accurate than social media because of certain characteristics like gatekeeping, cross-checking, etc. Although mainstream news (TV) organizations are facing a crisis like misinformation and disinformation because social media like Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, and Twitter are sharing and discussing news without the direct involvement of professional journalists (Bowd, 2016).

It is the role of media/TV journalists, reporters, and editors to filter the news in a very important and effective way. Television gatekeeping is a main conceptual assumption in creating distinctive pictures. Moviegoers can watch "Chup" to learn more about film reviewers and the impact they have on filmmakers and the industry (M. Kumar & Sharma, 2022). Whether or not spectators should be considered "gatekeepers" in today's social media era is an issue the film explores. News images typically rose to fame by being prominently displayed on prestigious media top stories. Elite media organizations have become the gatekeepers with the emergence of social media (Dahmen & Morrison, 2016). It depends upon the nature of the medium and other elements like timeliness, significance, proximity, human interest, etc. The ability to disseminate information and communicate with others is a key function of social media quickly and easily. Informational content can be sent to and gathered from the intended audience via these SNS using mobile applications. The total news cycle is affected by factors such as social media censorship and the pressure of political parties (satish Kumar et al., n.d.).

2.0 Review of literature

Gatekeeping is the process of culling and crafting countless bits of information into the limited number of messages that reach people each day. According to a study, media trustworthiness ratings were used to predict online fake political news exposure (FNE) among internet users in

five Gulf countries. In two of the five nations, respondents' news media credibility ratings negatively predicted FNE. Blocking bogus news online was this study's strongest finding (Martin & Hassan, 2020).

Gatekeeping curriculum in social work is vast. In a study, the authors explore the necessity and issues of gatekeeping in sociocultural work programs. The research evaluates the literature on gatekeeping in human work programs, addresses gatekeeping legal considerations, and outlines sociocultural work program obstacles to implementing gatekeeping processes. The study proposes integrating the council on social work Education's Educational Policy and Accreditation Standards (EPAS) for gatekeeping abilities in social work programs (Elpers & FitzGerald, 2013).

Media let people know about the news and provide a platform for people to get effective news. The more you filter the news and information, the more you get accurate and unbiased news and information (Ismail et al., 2019). As part of his study, the author herein analyses gatekeeping and the protest paradigm in a social media-driven news ecosystem. Since digital networks are changing the landscape of mainstream media, this research utilizes theme textual analysis to demonstrate that reporting of social protest in establishment media is not consistently clean.

Due to social media's dominance nowadays, editorial control is in the hands of the readers. The audience now chooses and directs how the story gets to the readers. The actual gatekeeper is therefore the audience. The audience obtains its news from a variety of sources, including Twitter and Facebook. This study seeks to understand media priming, veracity, and BJP-authorized post perception. They did the content analysis. The findings show that uncorked posts in the news are perceived neutrally and positively. BJP's tweets are not media primed. Mass media primes Twitter with celebrities, and inflammatory comments in the news (Sharma & Goyal, 2018).

Many aspects affect the news that is chosen. Reporters need to be aware of low-trust information, investigate every aspect of the live reporting environment, and explain to viewers why they are seeing what they are seeing and why not. Social networking sites on the internet have more fake news than traditional media outlets. They discover that more gatekeeping is necessary for online media to monitor legitimacy (Blassnig & Esser, 2022). The essential

component of any story is balance. However, the greatest disparities are in the political and audience spheres. The tale has been twisted to fit a different slant, which increases its fake news potential. Therefore, gatekeeping is urgently needed in the news to counteract inequality. When our study opens a wide window of gatekeepers on media news content and pinpoints the precise characteristics that control and affect news, we participate in the in-depth investigation (Peck, 2020).

3.0 Methodology: The present part of the study contains research objectives, research design, and sample design.

3.1 Research Objectives: The following are the research objectives.

Ro1: To know the factors affecting the news selection process in media.

Ro2: To investigate the financial and political effects of gatekeeping process in news media.

Ro3: To find out the relationship between the trending events on social media and the priming of events in mainstream media.

3.2 Research design:

We did descriptive research based on a quantitative approach and collected data with the survey method. We applied a questionnaire as a technique of data collection. We opted cross-sectional research design.

3.3 Sample design:

The universe is all the viewers/readers/listeners of mainstream media and social media. The population consists of all the viewers/readers/listeners who are university students. The sampling unit consists of media students at various universities in the Jaipur district.

3.4 Timeframe of the study:

We collected data between October 12 to December 2022.

3.5 Study variable:

We got the primary information from the survey and used nominal and ordinal scales to figure out the variables. In this study, we looked at dependent variables like political and commercial influence on news content, and impact on the selection of news for media.

3.6 Research tool:

We used Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0 to look at and analyze the data. We also put a lot of data on paper with the help of MS Office.

4.0 Analysis: The present analysis is based on simple percentage analysis.

4.1 Need of gatekeeping of the content broadcasted on DD and AIR.

Graph 4.1: Need for gatekeeping of the content broadcasted on DD and AIR.

A democratic government in any country needs to give the media the freedom and resources they need. Here, it's up to the media to make sure they don't take advantage of their power. India's Doordarshan and All India Radio have long been renowned for their respectable and well-balanced news coverage. Graph 4.1 indicates that 13% of total respondents firmly believe that gatekeeping is not necessary for the news content broadcast on Doordarshan and All India Radio. While 17.4% of respondents disagree with this notion. While 26.7% of respondents

believe that there should be some sort of gatekeeping of the content that is broadcast on AIR and Doordarshan, 6.6% of respondents are in complete agreement with this statement. The remaining 36.3% of respondents do not have a definite opinion regarding this issue.

4.2 Commercial effect on news media

Graph 4.2 Commercial effect on news media.

In the modern period, it is highly challenging to shield the media from the effect of commercialism. But, if news reporting's objectivity is entirely dominated by capitalism, democracy and the spirit of democracy suffer. Let's look at graph 4.2 to see how much sway the industry has over the media. Over half (54.1% to be exact) of those polled in the survey said that business played a role in shaping the news. About 17% of people are still not sure how they feel about this. Only 24% strongly agree with this statement. About 3% of people disagree with this notion, while 2.5% strongly disagree with the premise that the economy affects news.

4.3 The political effect on news media

Graph 4.3 The political effect on news media.

Politics is an essential part of the news. The impact of news implies political parties and political personalities, while political reactions also become a part of the news. In such a scenario, news media can also be influenced by politics, which forms a way wherein democracy and democratic feeling are frequently harmed. According to the data presented in graph 4.3, around 48% of all respondents agree with the statement that politics influences the news media, while 34.5% of individuals strongly agree with this viewpoint. On the other hand, approximately 6% of respondents disagree with this assumption, with 1.8% of those respondents strongly disagree.

4.4 The most impactful element for the selection of news in media

Graph 4.4: The most impactful element for the selection of news in media.

There is a lengthy procedure behind the presentation of news on DD and other mainstream media platforms. The news is influenced by several different factors. According to graph 4.4, a total of 30.4% of respondents feel that editors are responsible for the selection of news, while 26.7% of respondents believe that the management of the media organization is responsible for effective gatekeeping. The same 26.7% of respondents have the opinion that the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting is equally accountable for it. Approximately 17% of people believe that reporters are responsible, 8% of people believe that advertisers are responsible, and approximately 9% of people believe that other factors are responsible for the selection of news in media.

4.5 The most influence on the news content

Graph 4.5: The most influence on the news content.

The news content of a bulletin is the fundamental and most significant component that contributes to the podcast’s value, credibility, and popularity. But some other elements are contributing to news content selection. According to the data presented in graph 4.5, around 42% of all respondents believe that editors have the most effect on the content of the news, while 31.3% of people believe that reporters have the most influence on the substance of the news. On the other side, 15.1% of individuals think that sub-editors provide the same function, while approximately 12% choose not to use any available options.

4.6 Greatest influence on the acceptance or rejection of news

Graph 4.6: Greatest influence on the acceptance or rejection of news.

When deciding what news to publish, broadcast, or televise, various platforms use a variety of criteria. The judgement regarding the acceptance or disapproval of the news is based on several different internal and external factors. According to the data in graph 4.6, almost one-third of all individuals believe that political pressure is the primary factor that determines whether the information is accepted or rejected. While the influence of internal components of a media organization and economic pressure are similar at 21-21%, societal considerations account for 11.4% of the decision to refuse or approve news. On the other hand, 11.6% of people feel that additional reasons are also responsible for news selection and rejection.

4.7 The trending events on social media are prominently taken by news outlets.

Graph 4.7: The trending events on social media are prominently taken by news outlets.

The primary role of the media is to inform the general public about recent happenings. However, it is frequently seen that news outlets place a greater emphasis on the themes that are running on social media. Graph 4.7 shows that over half of all respondents agree, and 10.3% strongly agree, with the statement that news sources prominently publish and display popular events from social media. Besides that, 13% of people do not agree with this assertion, and roughly 3% people strongly disagree. However, 28.9% of persons consider themselves to have no opinion on this matter.

5.0 Result, discussion, and conclusion:

5.1 Result: More than one-third of the population supports censoring DD and AIR news content, while one-third of the population opposes it, and the remaining sixty-seven per cent have no opinion. The majority of respondents believe that financial considerations indeed influence the news media. Few people disagree with this notion, but about one-fifth of respondents are indifferent. More than three-quarters of all respondents believe that politics does affect the news media. Fewer than one in four people do not have an opinion on the topic, and an almost insignificant number of people hold the view that politics does not influence the news media.

Received: 12 Jan. 2023

Revised: 13 Feb 2023

Final Accepted for publication: 24 Feb 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

According to the poll results, two-fifths of all respondents believe that editors have the most effect on the topics covered in the news, while more than one-fourth of all people believe that reporters have the same amount of influence. Three out of twenty respondents believe that sub-editors have the most impact on the news content. About one-third of all participants believe that political pressure has the greatest impact on whether the news is acknowledged or rejected. One-fifth of individuals believe that commercial pressure and internal components of media organizations are equally influential in determining whether individuals accept or reject news. The research project demonstrates that three-fifths of people agree that news outlets make a big deal about events that are popular on social media. Nearly one-tenth of these people strongly agree with this statement. Less than one-third of people are not sure how they feel about this.

5.2 Discussions:

Meyer (Meyer, 2021) states in his/her study the impact of a court's press release on media vetting. This research looks at the frequency with which the media covers court news releases. The result indicates that news article being covered by the news increases when it contains specific principles, such as dispute, power and influence, consistency, or recognition. According to the scope of the present study financial pressure and the internal dynamics of media organizations have a considerable impact on the content of the news and play an essential role as gatekeepers.

Møller (Møller, 2022) seek to investigate the adoption of algorithmic news recommendations in the Nordic daily press. The current study describes the most influential factor in media news selection. We extended it as the management of media organization, the I&B ministry, journalists, and marketers also playing role in gatekeeping of news.

Salonen et al.(Salonen et al., 2022) explore their study of the post-publication gatekeeping process. They investigated the significance of social engagement and social dialogue in news. In addition, the present study delves deeply into editorial vetting in news media. The study also included the impact of economic and political issues on news gatekeeping.

Burkey (Burkey, 2019) pointed out in his study that multimedia consumers are both news spreaders and gatekeepers. While the current study investigates the impact of social media on

mainstream news selection. There is a positive synergy between the news of mainstream media and the trending issues on social media.

5.3 Conclusion:

People believe that content from DD and AIR should be regulated. People believe that political and economic factors impact the news selection process. Editors have a crucial role in the whole gatekeeping process. Political pressure strongly affects the acceptance or denial of news. Mainstream media outlets cover and promote trending stories on social media.

6.0 Reference:

- Blassnig, S., & Esser, F. (2022). The “Audience Logic” in digital journalism: An exploration of shifting news logics across media types and time. *Journalism Studies*, 23(1), 48–69.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2021.2000339>
- Bowd, K. (2016). Social media and news media: In M. Griffiths & K. Barbour (Eds.), *Making Publics, Making Places* (pp. 129–144). University of Adelaide Press; JSTOR.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.20851/j.ctt1t304qd.13>
- Bro, P., & Wallberg, F. (2015). Gatekeeping in a digital era. *Journalism Practice*, 9(1), 92–105.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2014.928468>
- Burkey, B. (2019). Millennials at the back gates: How young adults’ digital news practices present a new media logic for news gathering and gatekeeping as user-oriented activities in a participatory news ecosystem. *Media Practice and Education*, 20(4), 303–318.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/25741136.2018.1467681>
- Cherry, K. (2020, November 24). *Kurt Lewin and modern social psychology*. [Www.Verywellmind.Com](http://www.verywellmind.com).
<https://www.verywellmind.com/kurt-lewin-biography-1890-1947-2795540>

Dahmen, N. S., & Morrison, D. D. (2016). Place, space, time. *Digital Journalism*, 4(5), 658–678.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2015.1081073>

Elpers, K., & FitzGerald, E. A. (2013). Issues and challenges in Gatekeeping: A framework for implementation. *Social Work Education*, 32(3), 286–300.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2012.665867>

Ismail, A., Torosyan, G., & Tully, M. (2019). Social media, legacy media and gatekeeping: The protest paradigm in news of Ferguson and Charlottesville. *The Communication Review*, 22(3), 169–195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2019.1651153>

Kumar, Satish, Sharma, A., & Verma, V. (n.d.). *Social Media a Tool for Social and Political Inclusion among Youth: A Study of Indian University's Students*. 04, 82–89.

<https://doi.org/Doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.12944/CRJSSH.4.1.08>

Kumar, M., & Sharma, A. (2022). Save the cinema, kill the critic: Review of the film Chup: Revenge of the Artist (2022). *Media Asia*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01296612.2022.2136865>

Lewis, J. (2020). Identifying new gatekeepers in social media networks. *Hitotsubashi Journal of Social Studies*, 51(1), 77–86. JSTOR.

Martin, J. D., & Hassan, F. (2020). News media credibility ratings and perceptions of online Fake News exposure in five countries. *Journalism Studies*, 21(16), 2215–2233.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2020.1827970>

Meyer, P. (2021). Promoted media coverage of court decisions: Media gatekeeping of court press releases and the role of news values. *Journalism Studies*, 22(6), 723–740.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2020.1819861>

Møller, L. A. (2022). Recommended for you: How newspapers normalise algorithmic news recommendation to fit their gatekeeping role. *Journalism Studies*, 23(7), 800–817.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2022.2034522>

Peck, A. (2020). A problem of amplification: Folklore and fake news in the age of social media.

Journal of American Folklore, 133(529), 329–351.

<https://doi.org/10.5406/jamerfolk.133.529.0329>

Salonen, M., Olbertz-Siitonen, M., Uskali, T., & Laaksonen, S.-M. (2022). Conversational

Gatekeeping—Social interactional practices of post-publication gatekeeping on newspapers' Facebook pages. *Journalism Practice*, 1–25.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2022.2034520>

Sharma, A., & Goyal, A. (2018). Tweet, truth and fake news: A study of BJP's official Tweeter handle.

Journal of Content, Community and Communication, 4, 22–28.

<https://doi.org/10.31620/JCCC.12.18/05>

Soroka, S. N. (2012). The gatekeeping function: Distributions of information in media and the real world. *The Journal of Politics*, 74(2), 514–528. JSTOR.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s002238161100171x>

Steele, J. E. (2018). Censorship of library collections: An analysis using gatekeeping theory. *Collection*

Management, 43(4), 229–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01462679.2018.1512917>